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Research Overview of Factors Affecting Renewal Energy Development in Vietnam

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Received Date: 12-Aug-2021 Accepted Date: 28-Aug-2021 Published Date: 31-Aug-2021

Abstract:

The objective of the article is to review the research related to renewable energy development. From there, the study analyzes research gaps and proposes issues to be implemented in future research.

Keywords: *Renewable energy, renewable energy development, Vietnam*

1. Introduction

The process of global integration promotes the birth and promotes changes of machinery - technology. The 4.0 technology revolution and the severe impacts of climate change over the past decades have set an inevitable trend in the development of global renewable energy sources. Despite the serious effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, which led to a heavy decline in many energy sectors in general, "green energy" has always been focused on investment and development by countries.

A general overview of global "clean energy" sources according to the REN21 Global Renewable Energy Status Report (GSR) has given a general picture of favorable developments in the world energy transition with the goal is to get rid of the heavy dependence on fossil fuels that are gradually depleting. About a decade ago, conferences on green energy around the world have made many proposals to improve awareness and suggest directions in the application of renewable energy, which should be derived from interdisciplinary planning, model and model new business models and innovative applications of technology. Previous misconceptions have been refuted, "renewable energy is not something only developed countries can provide, but now, the world is witnessing a rapid paradigm shift in most of the world developing countries" (Report on the state of global renewable energy REN21). In particular, the motivation for countries to develop renewable energy sources mainly comes from four main reasons: mitigating climate change (the most important cause), ensuring energy security to adapt to climate change heavy impact from nature, rapid reduction of investment costs in renewable technology while increasing job opportunities, improving trade balance, promoting social welfare. Unremitting efforts have produced impressive results in terms of record capacity for new installations, investment costs falling rapidly for three years in a row, but also posed great challenges such as speed the growth rate is not commensurate with the potential of countries when investing in renewable energy development.

Overall, "the transition to renewable energy is accelerating thanks to both economic and environmental benefits" (Sam Kimmins, 2020) but obstacles are encountered as "multiple climate change policies are considered" are clichés" and especially "dependence on fossil fuels of nations" (Rana Adib, 2020). Many studies have come to sad conclusions from the Covid-19 pandemic when the authorities put the top priority of corporate profits, not "environmental benefits or public health" (Stephan Singer, 2020).

Worldwide, Vietnam has recorded the fastest economic growth in the region over the past few decades. Vietnam - the country of "golden forest, silver sea", possessing abundant natural energy and a long-standing agricultural economy; is a major supplier and exporter of rice in the world. Fossil energy sources in Vietnam create outstanding economic benefits for the country but are increasingly depleted due to the rapidly increasing demand of users and limited reserves. At the same time, the consumption of fossil energy sources poses a difficult problem about the serious environmental pollution effects caused. To solve this situation, new and renewable energy sources in Vietnam have been invested and developed, distributed throughout the country. In

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our country, the potential of geographical location, climate, agricultural economy, abundant renewable energy sources,.. are positive factors promoting the development of renewable energy sources. But besides many advantages of innovation and clean energy development, Vietnam also faces many barriers in the process of stability, long-term development and efficiency of "green energy".

In the face of positive developments and some backlogs and limitations in global renewable energy, many scholars have paid great attention to and researched the factors that promote or hinder the development of energy sources. regenerative. However, in Vietnam, there have not been many extensive studies on this field, there is a lack of appropriate models to apply renewable energy projects, awareness barriers in approaching investors due to lack of understanding clear benefits and risks involved (VEA report), difficulty in raising capital locally and limited resources in operation, maintenance and repair,.. Many institutional and legal barriers Technical and economic challenges that hinder Vietnam in practice are important issues that need to be resolved in a timely manner to improve the quality and development of renewable energy sources across the country.

2. Literature review

In recent times, research on renewable energy has been noticed and exploited based on many different research directions. But mainly the general research on renewable energy, renewable energy development studies and research on the barriers of renewable energy. From previous studies, the study points out gaps and problems related to the development of renewable energy.

2.1. Research on renewable energy

Renewable energy plays an important role in the sustainable growth of a country. The government always needs energy plans and strategies in line with the goals of integration and sustainable development.

According to Muvaney (2006) defines that electrical energy can generally be understood as electricity generated through many conversions between other forms of energy such as chemical, nuclear, thermal, mechanical and potential gravity. The general conversion is heat to mechanical to electrical, but operation may vary depending on the resource used. Fossil fuels make the largest contribution to electric energy production because of their high energy content and provide two-thirds of the world's electrical energy needs. However, burning fossil fuels in the process of generating electricity will produce carbon dioxide, which causes the greenhouse effect and environmental pollution. That is why renewable energy has become an indispensable option when comparing the impact of this type of energy with traditional energy sources on the environment.

Bao (2010) argues that non-renewable energy is a very important source of energy for mankind. Thanks to this energy source, human society has enough energy to survive and develop. Renewable energy - an energy source that can ensure sustainable and safe development for people. Researchers, scientists, and environmentalists all agree that generating electricity from renewable resources does not cause as much negative impact on the environment as generating electricity from fossil fuels. As (Sathaye et al, 2007) has confirmed that renewable energy contributes to several important sustainable development goals: (1) economic and social development; (2) energy access; (3) energy security; (4) mitigating climate change and reducing environmental and health impacts. Mitigating dangerous man-made climate change is seen as a powerful driver behind the increased use of renewable energy worldwide. This opinion is also agreed (Cook, 2012) when he writes that using renewable energy is one of the simplest and most effective ways to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. This author used to be the Director of the Petroleum Collaborative Research Center (PCRC) in Australia, so he is very concerned about climate change related to clean energy.

According to (Cook, 2012) renewable energy sources will be substituted for main energy sources in terms of CO₂ emission reduction. Environmentally friendly renewable energy must be encouraged, promoted, implemented and demonstrated by scale development and especially for use in remote rural areas (Aiden, 2011). Biomass and hydroelectricity are the two main clean energy sources being used today in Vietnam. In the

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future, these sources will be continued to be used and are expected to be supplemented with wind and solar power (EOR19 Report, 2019).

2.2. Research on renewable energy development

In just the past year, Vietnam has made strong strides in renewable energy development. Especially with the record of new solar power capacity put into operation, Vietnam has become one of the most vibrant and attractive renewable energy markets in Southeast Asia at the moment. However, the rapid development of this energy source over the past time is posing new challenges in terms of the synchronous development of the grid system, the electricity price mechanism, etc.

Renewable energy development is the development of the following energy sources:

Small hydroelectric power: small hydroelectric power is produced from water energy with small and renewable capacity. From the rivers and streams flowing from the source to the sea, they all carry a potential of energy (hydropower). Usually, the source of hydroelectricity depends on the slope of the river and stream and the flow of water flowing through it. Hydropower sources can be evenly or unevenly distributed over a section of rivers and streams. To concentrate the energy of the flow by creating a water level difference between the upstream and downstream, some methods of hydroelectric power stations are used such as: dams, pipelines or synthesis. Small hydroelectricity is often exploited in mountainous areas where many small rivers and streams are concentrated. This is a cheap energy source, so it is necessary to have an effective exploitation and use policy. In Vietnam, since 2007, the Ministry of Industry and Trade has defined small hydroelectricity as hydroelectricity with a capacity not exceeding 30MW and is considered a source of electricity from renewable energy.

Wind energy: is the kinetic energy of air moving through the earth's atmosphere. Wind energy is a transitional form of solar energy, because it is daylight that heats the atmosphere, creating a temperature and pressure difference between different regions, creating the phenomenon of wind blowing evenly over the earth's surface. Wind energy is considered environmentally and socially friendly.

Solar energy: is the energy of the flow of electromagnetic radiation from the Sun plus a small part of the energy from other primordial particles emitted from the Sun. This is an extremely important source of energy for the existence and development of life on earth, and is also the source of other forms of renewable energy such as wind energy, biomass energy, etc. . and is considered endless.

Geothermal energy: Geothermal is a natural energy source under one crust of the Earth, the temperature is up to 1000°C - 40000C, some areas the pressure exceeds 130MPa. This is an infinite source of energy generated from the chain of nuclear reactions, the decomposition of radioactive substances regularly in the Earth's interior such as Thorium (Th), Protactinium (Pa), Uranium (U)...etc. melting the earth's core under high pressure. Usually, to exploit geothermal energy, it is only necessary to drill wells 4-5km deep to reach a temperature of about 2000C. Boiled water will follow the pipe up and can run the generators...etc. According to experts, about 10% of the Earth's crust contains geothermal resources that can be assessed with potential, and these sources can provide a very large source of energy.

Tidal energy: is the energy produced by the ebb and flow of the tides. People take advantage of the movement of ocean waves or tidal activity to generate electricity. Those methods all use a special type of generator to convert tidal energy into electricity. However, this form of energy is still in the research and development stage.

Biomass energy: biomass includes plants that grow and develop on land as well as in water, organic wastes such as rice straw, rice husks, bagasse, coffee husks..., animal wastes such as human excrement, cattle and poultry manure.... Biomass is a renewable energy source that exists and develops thanks to sunlight. Plants absorb sunlight to carry out photosynthesis reactions, converting minerals, water and other inorganic elements

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into organic substances. Photosynthesis is also the basic reaction that creates food for animals. During photosynthesis, plants also absorb carbon dioxide and produce oxygen, which is the gas that creates life on earth.

Economic factors create competitive advantages of renewable energy compared to conventional energy of fossil fuels. Recognizing the positives and negatives of clean energy development and fossil energy influence investors' decisions. This is one of the biggest challenges affecting renewable energy choices in most countries. Some authors have pointed out that the cost of generating electricity from renewable energy is higher than that from fossil fuels, so it will not be widely used by countries. It may be true about the investment costs. As (Cook, 2012) analyzed that the power plant's cost per unit of generating capacity, which ranges from a base case of \$1200 - \$1300 per kilowatt for a combined cycle gas turbine, does not carbon capture and storage (CCS) to \$190000 - \$2300 per kilowatt with CCS. The capital cost for black coal (supercritical) power plant with CCS is estimated by Burgess at \$2900 - \$4500 per kilowatt versus \$2100-\$2900 per kilowatt for wind. Solar PV ranges from \$4600 - \$5700 per kilowatt depending on the PV system and geothermal is in the \$4000 - \$6300 per kilowatt range (Cook, 2012). This is also agreed upon by (Shen, 2014) when he calculates that the unit cost of coal-fired electricity generation is 350 Yuan/kWh, while the cost of wind and solar energy production is 620 and 1900 Yuan/kWh (1 Chinese Yuan equals 0.16 US dollars in 2013), (Shen, 2014).

Of course, if countries only looked at these numbers, they would not choose renewable energy for development. However, a study conducted by experts from the International Renewable Energy Agency (IREA) shows an opposite view. After analyzing all the relevant costs of a renewable power plant (solar and wind) such as investment costs, operation and maintenance costs, insurance and interest, the calculation proved demonstrated that Bi-Biassass for electricity, hydro, geothermal and onshore wind can now provide competitive electricity, compared to fossil fuel-fired energy production. It is developments in new wind and solar renewable energy generation technologies, however, that have pushed the addition of renewable generation capacity to record levels. An ethical policy circle promoting deployment, technology innovation, and cost reductions has seen onshore wind become one of the most competitive options for next-generation capacity. The decentralized cost of electricity (LCOE) of solar cells fell by 58% between 2010-2015, making it increasingly competitive at a utility scale. Despite the fact that centralized solar (CSP) and offshore wind are in the early stages of deployment, these technologies are already attractive in some markets, with costs continuing to fall (IRENA, Energy). change to solar energy and reduce wind costs by 2025).

2.3. Study of barriers affecting the development of renewable energy

Academic research in renewable energy (RE) is divided into several disciplines, including engineering, economics, political science, and sociology. Economists have played an important role in understanding the key factors that either stimulate or hinder the development of renewable energy (Karatayev et al., 2016). There are many different factors proposed by different researchers, in this study, the author summarizes the following four factors: Social barriers, economic barriers, technological barriers and legal barriers. Research on the development of renewable energy in Vietnam has been identified with the following main difficulties and barriers (EOR17 Report, 2017): (i) Technical barriers: lack of project development capacity, poor infrastructure, technology dependence. (ii) Institutional barriers: there is no national plan for renewable energy, policies and mechanisms to support renewable energy are not enough to attract investors, and electricity prices are low. (iii) Economic barriers: relatively large initial investment capital, difficulty in accessing loans. (iv) Market barriers: lack or inability to access information on potentials and technologies of renewable energy.

- Social barriers

The transition from conventional resources to renewable energy has met with resistance and public outcry. This is due to a lack of awareness about the benefits of renewable energy, disrupting the seascape and acquiring land that can be used for agriculture, tourism, etc. (Goldsmiths, 2015).

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Public awareness and information barriers: Sustainable development is rooted in the satisfaction of human desires, through socially recognized technological systems and appropriate policies and regulatory tools. (Paravantis et al., 2014). The main concerns regarding public understanding are: 1) insufficient information regarding ecological and financial benefits; 2) inadequate awareness of renewable energy technology; and 3) uncertainty about the financial viability of RE installation projects (Nasirov et al., 2015).

People often support renewables in general, but not in their own neighborhoods. Renewable power project proposals are often met with opposition from individual citizens, political leaders, grassroots organizations, national interest groups and, in some cases, even environmental groups (Jianjun et al. Chen, 2014). Public outcry occurs for a number of reasons, including landscape impact, environmental degradation, and lack of interest in consultation among local communities (Nasirov et al., 2015).

Loss of Alternative/Alternative Income: A major problem with renewable plants (especially solar and wind farms) is that large areas of land are needed to produce an equivalent amount of energy. amount can be produced from a small coal-fired power plant (Chauhan and Saini, 2015). To make a significant contribution to global energy consumption, it is necessary to develop large-scale renewable energy plants, but this requires large premises. A lot of the countryside, including farmland, needs to be converted into buildings or roads or any other infrastructure to support a renewable energy plant. To achieve this, other sectors such as agriculture and tourism may be affected (Nesamalar et al., 2017).

Lack of experienced professionals: The global transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources requires a strong foundation of a skilled workforce. Therefore, the need for skilled professionals to design, build, operate and maintain a renewable energy plant is great. Incompetent technical experts and lack of well-trained institutes have prevented the development of renewable energy (Ansari et al., 2016). Appropriate renewable energy training is required to develop the skills needed to install and operate renewable energy projects. The lack of a trained workforce to design, finance, construct, operate and maintain renewable energy projects is considered a major obstacle to the widespread development of renewable energy. (Karakaya and Sriwannawit, 2015).

- Economic barriers

Factors affecting economic and financial barriers are high initial capital, lack of financial institutions, lack of investors, competition from fossil fuels and less subsidies compared to traditional fuels (Raza) et al., 2015). These factors have prevented renewable energy from becoming widespread.

Fierce competition from fossil fuels: Fossil fuels will remain the main competitor in energy supply in the future. The International Energy Outlook (2016) report shows that fossil fuels (oil, natural gas and coal) are expected to provide 78% of global energy used by 2040. Fossil fuel investment (including electricity supply and generation) for 55% of global energy investment in 2016, compared with 16% for renewables. Coal remains the predominant fuel source in most countries of the world because coal is abundant, cheap and easily accessible (Dulal et al., 2013). There have been major changes in energy since the summer of 2014. Oil, as measured by the Brent crude contract, was priced at \$115.71 per barrel in June 2014, falling to \$27.10 per barrel in January 20, 2016, a huge decrease of 76%. Similarly, the ARA coal contract fell from \$84/ton in April 2014 to \$36.30 in February 2016. Natural gas prices fell sharply, down from around \$4.50 in June 2014 to \$1.91 in mid-February 2016. As prices fall, fossil fuels are still emerging as a cheaper alternative to renewables, which could offer competition. harsh for renewable energy projects.

Government funding and subsidies: The amount of government subsidies provided for conventional energy is much higher than those given to renewable energy. This puts renewables at a disadvantage over fossil fuels. Government-provided subsidies to generate electricity from fossil fuel sources are overshadowing the widespread use of low-emission technologies. For example, coal companies in Australia and Indonesia still receive government subsidies for mining and exploration (Dulal et al., 2013).

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Fewer financial institutions: Renewable energy developers and producers face serious difficulties in securing financing for renewable energy projects that are much lower than those of projects. fossil fuel energy (Ansari et al., 2016). There are limited financial instruments available to organizations to finance renewable projects. This reflects that investments are considered somewhat risky, thus discrediting investors (Ohunakin et al., 2014).

High Initial Capital Cost: Renewable energy projects require high initial capital costs and, due to the lower efficiency of renewable technology, a high net payback period, which puts investors in a position hind legs (Ansari et al., 2016). Both users and manufacturers can have very low capital and to install a plant they need funding. This problem is further underscored by strict lending measures that limit access to financing even when funding is available for conventional energy projects (Suzuki, 2013). Capital costs are high, often underfunded, and most importantly, projects with high payback periods often become unviable (Painuly. J, 2001).

Intangible costs: Currently, in most countries, the total cost of fuel includes the cost of exploration, production, distribution and use, but does not include the cost of damage to the environment and society. Despite the serious effects on health and the atmosphere, the unseen (external) costs associated with traditional fuels are not included in their prices (Arnold, 2015). Understanding these impacts is essential to assessing the real costs of using fossil fuels for energy production.

- Technological barriers

Another important factor influencing the development of renewable energy is technology. In 2008, the World Bank published a very interesting article on clean energy called Accelerating Research, Development and Deployment of Clean Energy Technologies (Avato, 2008). Publications present valuable lessons from the non-energy sector. First of all, the authors of this work have confirmed that better and broader use of existing clean energy technologies can play an important role in mitigating climate change (Avato, 2008). However, they complain that most of these technologies are too expensive or unreliable to deploy in research and development. The reasons for this situation are many. One of them is that renewable energy technology is still in the early stages of development or has not been fully commercialized. Research and development costs are enormous. To overcome the barriers, the authors conducted case studies of four non-energy sectors to find solutions. As the authors say, although each case study examined has its own unique circumstances that differ from the clean energy industry, the similarities and innovative approaches used in Research, Development and Implementation can provide valuable lessons (Avato, 2008). In particular, there are a number of legitimate technological barriers to the widespread deployment of renewable energy, including limited infrastructure, inefficient operation and maintenance knowledge, research and incomplete development, and technical complexity such as energy storage and no standards (Zhao et al., 2016).

Infrastructure and facilities: Advanced technology is needed for renewable energy development, especially in developing countries. Even when renewable energy technologies are available, procurement costs are very high (Dulal et al., 2013). Since renewable energy plants are mostly located in remote locations, additional transmission lines to connect to the main grid need to be added. Since most existing grids are not designed to integrate with renewable energy, these existing grids need to be upgraded or modified (Izadbakhsh et al., 2015). Grid integration is one of the biggest issues affecting the development of renewable energy projects.

Lack of operation and maintenance culture: Since renewable energy technology is relatively new and not optimally developed, there is a lack of knowledge about operation and maintenance. Efficiency cannot be achieved if a plant is not operated optimally and if maintenance is not performed regularly (Sen and Bhattacharyya, 2014). Lack of equipment, components and spare parts will significantly increase production costs, since these items need to be imported from other countries, high purchase prices and production will increase overall costs (Bhandari et al., 2015).

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Lack of research and development (R&D) capabilities: Investments in research and development (R&D) are not sufficient to generate renewable energy that is commercially competitive with fossil fuels. Both the government and energy companies are reluctant to spend on R&D because renewable energy is in the development stage and the risks associated with this technology are very high (Cho et al., 2013).

Technological complexity: There are not enough standards, processes and guidelines in renewable energy technology in terms of durability, reliability, efficiency, etc... This makes renewable energy difficult to achieve commercialized on a large scale (Nasirov et al., 2015). A major technical problem that renewables are facing today is energy storage. To solve these problems, it is necessary to develop large batteries that can compensate for the time when there are no renewable resources (Weitemeyer et al., 2014).

- Policy barriers, legal regulations

Factors such as lack of national policies, administrative barriers, government policies and lack of standards and guidelines have significantly hindered the development of renewable energy (Stokes, 2013).

Inefficient government policies: Strong regulatory policies in the energy sector are not only necessary for a country's sustainable development, but also address the inconsistency between renewable and non-renewable energy. Lack of effective policies creates confusion among different departments in the implementation of subsidies. Major issues such as unstable energy policy, insufficient confidence in renewable energy, lack of policies to integrate renewable energy with the global market are barriers to the implementation of energy projects renewable energy (Zhang et al., 2014).

Inadequate financial incentives: The government has not done enough to eliminate taxes on imports of equipment and parts needed for renewable energy plants. Feed tariffs are measures by which governments aim to subsidize renewable energy sources to make them cost-competitive with fossil fuel-based technologies, but the Having these adequate financial incentives leads to high costs hindering the development of renewable energy (Sun and Nie, 2015).

Administrative and bureaucratic complexity: The obstacles that arise in implementing renewable energy projects are diverse, including administrative barriers such as delays in handling administrative procedures. There is a lack of coordination between different agencies and it takes a lot of time to get permission for a project. Higher costs are also associated with obtaining permission from lobbying, informal costs. All these factors prolong project start-up time and reduce the incentive needed to invest in renewable energy development (Ahlborg & Hammar, 2014).

Government commitment: There is a gap between the policy goals set by the government and the actual results realized when implemented (Goldsmiths, 2015). The policies set forth by the government are sometimes difficult to implement in practice, leading to a conflict between the policy prescribed by law and the reality. Therefore, the government must take measures to make regulations and policies sensitive and suitable to actual circumstances, to promote and develop renewable energy towards the goal of sustainable development of the country.

Lack of specific government standards and guidelines: Standards and certifications are required to ensure that equipment and parts manufactured or purchased abroad conform to the standards of the importing company. export. These certifications ensure that companies operating factories comply with local laws. Lack of such standards creates confusion and energy producers face unnecessary difficulties (Emodi et al., 2014).

3. Conclusion

Many studies around the world on renewable energy have shown the factors that promote the development of renewable energy or the factors that are the barriers to the development of renewable energy. However, there has been no research that simultaneously analyzes these two factors and shows how the group of barriers and motivating factors affect the development of renewable energy today. Researching and at the

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same time showing the impact that has the effect of promoting or creating barriers plays an extremely important role in research and development of renewable energy research.

There are many previous studies using many different models and theories, but none have used Herzberg's two-factor theory and the theory of energy justice to explain the research model. The use of this theory plays an important role in the rigorous analysis and evaluation of the process of building and selecting models, arguments and explanations in the research paper.

The use of the theory of energy equity plays the role of proving the trend of renewable energy development is indispensable for each country to ensure energy equity and sustainability in development. At the same time, the study successfully used Herzberg's two-factor theory - a theory widely applied by managers around the world - as a basis for arguing about the group of two factors: motivating factors and human factors barriers to the development of renewable energy in Vietnam. Herzberg's two-factor theory plays an important role in planning policies and measures to promote sustainable and efficient renewable energy development, minimize barriers, improve quality and increase take good care of the general environment.

Research considers renewable energy to be anthropomorphized. That means renewable energy uses both resources: one that tends to promote and the other to be a limiting barrier. That helps to generalize and overcome many gaps from research before research and analysis on renewable energy. Since then, the research shows that the government's policies on renewable energy development are absolutely right, bringing many benefits to the country, protecting health and increasing jobs for people. Measures from the government on renewable energy development need to be stronger, setting clearer goals for green energy development.

Researchers, scientists, and environmentalists all agree that generating electricity from renewable resources does not cause as much negative impact on the environment as generating electricity from fossil fuels. Mitigating dangerous man-made climate change is seen as a powerful driver behind the increased use of renewable energy worldwide. This opinion is also agreed (Cook, 2012) when he writes that using renewable energy is one of the simplest and most effective ways to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. This author used to be the Director of the Petroleum Collaborative Research Center (PCRC) in Australia, after his research he expressed concern about climate change related to clean energy. Does the development of clean energy sources have climate change associated with them? Currently, there are no studies to address this issue.

However, the rapid development of this energy source over the past time is posing new challenges in terms of the synchronous development of the grid system, the electricity price mechanism, etc. Mainstream wind power development mainly concentrated in the South, the Central Highlands and the South Central region. Therefore, the transmission grid may not develop in time to connect all solar and wind power projects. However, most researches in Vietnam have not studied synchronous solutions and solving limitations in the network system related to "clean energy".

Currently, there are no studies on the approach and effective use of capital in clean energy projects of enterprises in Vietnam. Renewable energy developers and producers face serious difficulties in securing financing for renewable energy projects that are much lower than those of fossil fuel energy projects. Ansari et al., 2016). There are financial instruments that limit institutions to financing renewable projects, which reflects that investments are considered somewhat risky, thus discrediting investors (Ohunakin et al. ., 2014).

Using renewable energy is very important not only to meet energy needs but also to solve the problems of climate change (Byrnes et al., 2013). However, barriers (social, economic, technological and regulatory) exist in this sector that prevent the growth and penetration of renewable energy globally. Countries with overly complex administrative procedures have less renewable energy development than countries with simple procedures (Huang et al., 2013). Energy is the backbone for the socio-economic development of any country (Raza et al., 2015). By using more renewable energy sources, countries can help fulfill energy shortfalls without damaging nature. The impact of this change will be to create more jobs in the design, construction, operation

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and maintenance of renewable energy project infrastructure. A higher degree of diffusion will help achieve economies of scale, and that will reduce costs and therefore prices for the end user. This will improve investor confidence and will trigger increased investment in renewable energy projects. Greater benefits can be reaped from available green energy as there will be no serious impact on the environment and that can help maintain the earth's ecology. Most of the previous studies have not found the factors that promote the improvement of investor confidence and the increase in the development of renewable energy in the country. How to promote government policies in renewable energy development?

The above issues show that the study of factors affecting the development of renewable energy in Vietnam is really necessary in terms of both theory and practice of development policy. However, current studies still have many limitations in the process of finding "factors affecting the success of renewable energy development in Vietnam?", pointing out "which factors play an important role. most important?" and proposed "what recommendations can help sustainable development of renewable energy in Vietnam?"

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